

3. An 'African nuclear physics' recognises how the 'four-interactive-forces' that physics has identified in the atoms, are equally here within and between us humans. They are especially evident in family life.

In this mood, look again at the Mushroom Cloud and see how it portrays the marriage of the feminine and masculine 'entities' who form themselves from the copious quantities of energy released out of matter by the fission process.

I came to the nuclear subject as a consequence of working as a geologist in Canada, where I was involved in a search for uranium. That work made me curious about the nature of the energy in the atoms. I firstly learnt about the '**four-interactive-forces**', which nuclear physics has determined are in each and every atom. These four forces are known everywhere as:

Gravity and **Electromagnetism** (which are long range forces), and **The Strong** and **the Weak** Nuclear Forces (which are short range forces (in other words, they only function within the boundary of each atom)). Together they form what we know casually as 'nuclear energy'.

I recognised early on how physics identifies these forces on the basis of their objective properties. Being as I am an introspective person, this caused me to wonder about their subjective qualities. What, for instance, might they feel like.

During this time, when I was wondering about the subjective qualities of the 'four forces', my wife and I were busy as anything with raising our three young children. Our home was brimful with the children's activities and demands and needs. In the hurly burly of it all, I slowly came to see how the four energetic qualities that physics has identified in the atoms, these same energetic qualities were equally here at work and play in the daily dynamic of family life. I now see how they are in every family system, little or large. And not just in us humans. The 'four forces' look to be at work in every species, and present at every level of this multi-tiered universal system that we are within. Here is how I have come to see the subjective qualities of the 'four forces'.

Gravity, often categorised as the first of the four forces, is a quality I easily recognise in myself. I am a serious character, full of gravity, 'heavy' about everyday subjects. Gravititas dominates my demeanour. Gravity is clearly a masculinity quality. It finds expression in me as a fairly authoritarian father. The same quality that was in my father, and his. Nothing especially new then in my archetypal make up.

I dwell on the analogy of **Gravity** being synonymous with **Masculinity** because it exemplifies the dualistic process whereby we can take an objective description of physical phenomena (such as this energetic force), and by dwelling on our experience of how this force feels and functions, we can identify the metaphysical and subjective nature of this universal effect.

Whereas **Gravity** is an ambitious and commanding vertical force ... **Electromagnetism**, on the other hand, is an entirely feminine power.

Electromagnetism, physically and psychically, is a friendly family-centred motherly power that emanates and spreads horizontally from her centre. The magnetic power of this forces reaches out to permeate the surrounding area and hears and feels the emotional state of everything in this territory. At home in a family setting, this is the inquisitive mothering consciousness that likes to know how everyone in the house is doing, how they are feeling, and what their needs are.

The short-range forces:

Physics knows the **Strong Nuclear Force** as the 'binding energy' that holds each atom together. It is a collective elastic-like power that works to stabilise every atom and every family system. It is an essential quality because competing forces continually arise within every atom or family unit: forces which threaten to split the unit apart. I sense that the **Strong Force** is equivalent to the "family spirit", to the collective energy, the love and loyalty, little or large that each member/particle of the family/atom contributes to the whole system.

In contrast, the **Weak Nuclear Force** is a miniscule quantity of energy that was discounted as experimental error in the early days of particle physics. Further investigation then determined that this is indeed an individual force, and its identifying characteristics are that it only functions across a very short distance, and only exists for a brief moment of time. But in that moment, it is more powerful than all the other forces. Now, doesn't this sound and feel like sexual energy. The **Weak Force** works as a catalyst, and combines with **Electromagnetism** and **Gravity** to make them interact and be fruitful and productive.

I would mention here that astrophysicists calculated in the 1930's how the 'four forces' were seeded into our universal system in the beginning moments of the Big Bang. Around this same time, nuclear physicists determined how these four forces are in each and every atom. Thus we know full well they are in the macrocosm and the microcosm. Now we dearly needs to realise how the 'four forces' are equally here at work in us humans. We can not recognise this if we close the door on subjective data and effect. Once we realise the social and spiritual nature of these forces, how they work together to create and maintain family systems, then our Universe becomes yet more sensible and uniform in its processes and behaviour.

The band-width of the information about the 'four forces' indicates they are universal forces. To my mind, this means that however we might seek to identify them, we will in the end only recognise the qualities that match our particular interest. Physics knows them for their physical properties. The religious for their spiritual qualities. In the home, we know the 'four forces' for their homely and domestic and social nature.

"The Four-interactive-Forces" and the different nomenclature we give to them, according to the purpose of our inquiry.		
The terminology of Nuclear Physics, as it identifies the objective properties in each atom.	Domestic household language as we recognise the subjective nature of each force in the family.	Christian synonyms that seek to name the spiritual quality of each force.
Gravity	Masculine Strength	Light of God
Electromagnetism	Feminine Power	Amos
The Strong Nuclear Force	Family Group Energy	Agape
The Weak Nuclear Force	Sexual Energy	Eros

This table conveys the family-centred nature of this multi-tiered universal system we are all within. Here is a good place to re-iterate how my experience of these four forces indicates that three of them are forms of Love, while the fourth is a form of Light.

Meanwhile, observe how, in our modern era, nuclear physics has grabbed the talking stick and thinks these 'four forces' are theirs alone. This is not so. They live in all of us, and all of the time. Our civil nature needs to equally claim ownership and responsibility for their sensible use.

The metaphysics of the Mushroom Cloud.

The same energy in the atoms as in us humans suggests we must expect to find the same energetic processes going on in the particle world as engage us humans in our world. In this context, look again at the Mushroom Cloud that forms itself in the aftermath of every nuclear detonation.

This series of photographs come from a nuclear weapon test carried out by the French military in the South Pacific, circa 1970. I have however borrowed the first image from an American test, because it very clearly shows the formative beginning moment of this almighty process. The photographs allow us to see how the copious quantities of masculine (Gravity) and feminine (Electromagnetism) energy released out of the atoms by the fission process, then form (at the speed of Light) the two pantomime-like "energetic entities" that together initiate and create the whole Mushroom Cloud drama.

The Mushroom Cloud portrays the meeting and marriage of the feminine and masculine "energetic entities" who form themselves (at the speed of Light) from the energy released out of the atoms by the fission process.

Young lovers

The married couple. Her power the equal of his strength.

Each partner busy developing their own talents. His ambition is

to reach his full potential. While she cloaks herself with emotional powers.

Her destiny is to be the motherly queen, supported by his princely gravity.

Observe in the first image, how the muscular masculine 'entity' rises with love and longing to meet the soft rounded honeybun-figure of the feminine 'entity', waiting above where he is. We can see already the relationship forming between them. The Mushroom Cloud is basically a visual record of their union and indeed, their marriage to each other.

We can recognise and follow their process because it is entirely similar to our human experience of the marriage cycle. The atomic version completes itself in about fifty seconds of our time, whereas we humans can take fifty years to fulfil the same phases that they work through, in their Atomic World existence.

Nuclear fission works for us, in our reactors, by breaking up the atoms of uranium. By this means we gain access to the heat of the Light quotient that is in each and every atom. Light (amalgamated with Gravity) is one of the four forces. The three other forces (which are forms of Love) are discarded because they have no calorific value, and are useless for boiling water, which is the primary purpose of a nuclear reactor.

In the vein of inquiry that values subjective data, our nuclear work allows us to see how the atomic particles are social and sentient, the same as we are. They are in turn as small to us as we are small to the Sun. This kind of understanding helps us see them as the children of this universal system that we are all within. Gulliver would have recognised all of this if he was traveling today. The same energy, the same energetic processes amongst the particles as is here in us humans allows us to recognise how 'radioactivity' is a measure of the emotional distress of the fissioned particles. Fission works for us by annihilating the family systems that together create the particle nation of Uranium. This is the reality we dearly need to see and own.

The last clear image we have of the whole fission process shows how the "feminine archetype" has transformed herself into a regal and matriarchal entity.

She has the demeanour and deportment of a Queen. She is commanding and matronly. This surely indicates the quality of the consciousness that has developed within her, during this whole marriage cycle.

See, by the way, also how the fabric of the Queen's electromagnetic dress is torn. We can see swirls of Mr Gravity's golden energy, the metaphysical stuff that forms his upright frame, is now leaking out of the enclosing gown, yet continues to migrate upwards.

Upwards is indeed the main direction of the Atomic man's enthusiasm and drive to get as high as he can with his life energy.

Everyone has countless reasons for believing in the separate self. For staying away from evidence of our universal nature. Observe the fission process from this part of ourselves and see how we are watching a marriage ceremony at the beginning, and then how this 'energetic universal couple', created from the energy that was in the atoms, then live collaboratively together while developing their particular talents.

This is an entirely sensible and symmetrical Universe. The same universal forces are at work and play between us humans, as are between and amongst the atomic particles, as are upstairs between the Sun and the Moon.

The nuclear weapon tests reveal as never before the longing for the creative co-operative union that is between feminine and masculine forms of energy. The very forces that our nuclear technology casually releases out of their shared bed in matter.

Do the military or the nuclear institutions know this? Not yet. They have been schooled and school themselves to look away. This is primarily a civilian observation. In which case, we civilians must develop civil ways to engage with this deeper knowledge.

